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Negative CO₂ Emissions in Cement and Waste-to-Energy Plants: Integration of Calcium-Looping, CO₂ Purification and Mineralization Processes within the HERCCULES project

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Abstract

The Horizon Europe HERCCULES project is an innovation action aimed at assessing the whole CCUS chain in southern Europe, focusing on the cement and energy-from-waste sectors. A significant effort to achieve this ambitious goal is dedicated to demonstrating CO₂ capture and utilization technologies. Three capture technologies will be tested in the cement industry: an amine-based solvent absorption system to assess the performance of a new generation solvent using several configurations and including innovative components; an oxyfuel calciner coupled with a CPU to evaluate the possibility of achieving a capture rate of around 80% without modifying the key steps of the clinker production process; and the hybrid configuration to achieve an overall capture rate of 98%. Meanwhile, a CaL system coupled with a cryogenic CPU will be demonstrated in the EfW plant. Three CO₂ utilization technologies will be tested: an autoclave system for the production of autoclaved hydraulic binders, a skid for the mineralization of fine demolished concrete, and a zeolite-based mineralization plant to produce CO₂-trapped natural and synthetic zeolite to be used as SCMs. Currently, all the capture and utilization technologies are in the design and procurement stage, and next year, the experimental campaign will begin. Finally, CO₂ storage will be tested, and the development of the whole CCUS chain will be optimized for the northern Italy and Greece clusters. Exploitation material, business plans, and guidelines for all the technologies demonstrated, as well as a life cycle assessment and cost-benefit analysis of the whole CCUS, will be delivered at the end of the project.

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1. Introduction

In 2022, the cement sector contributed to the direct emission of 2'356 Mt_{CO₂}, without including the indirect contribution from electricity consumption, corresponding to 6.2% of the global energy-related greenhouse gas emission [1]. The cement industry is considered a hard-to-abate sector due to two main key characteristics: (i) around 60% of the CO₂ released derives from the calcination of the raw material (mainly limestone - CaCO₃), so-called process emissions, and (ii) the calcination process requires high-temperature heat, which is difficult to generate without the combustion of fossil fuel. In the short term, improvements in energy efficiency, lowering the clinker-to-cement ratio, electrification and using low-emission fuels are key but insufficient emission reduction measures to meet the Net Zero Emission scenario targets [2]. Deep emission reductions require innovative technologies, such as cement production from alternative raw materials and Carbon Capture Utilization and Storage (CCUS) technologies [2]. To achieve the emissions targets set for 2030, the International Energy Agency (IEA) indicates that 12% of the total heat required for the clinker production process will need to be generated with carbon capture technologies, and this fraction will increase to 50% in 2050 [2]. Thus, accelerating the development of such processes is of crucial importance. Partial oxyfuel is one of the most attractive options due to its relatively simple integration into a conventional cement plant [3–6], minimizing retrofittability complexity by using oxy-combustion only in the pre-calciner and leaving essentially unchanged the core of the clinker production process, represented by the rotary kiln and clinker cooler. However, partial oxyfuel can only achieve capture rates in the order of 70% and it should be integrated with other CO₂ capture systems to achieve a higher decarbonization level, e.g., an amine-based solvent plant, by capturing the CO₂ generated in the rotary kiln.

Another hard-to-abate sector of particular interest in the application of CO₂ capture systems in recent years, especially since the decision of the European Parliament to include these plants in the CO₂ European Trading Systems (ETS) (likely starting from 2026-28), is the Energy-from-Waste (EfW) sector [2]. However, the combustion of unsorted waste in grate-fired boilers is one of the key pillars of the waste management chain, and, due to the presence of a biogenic share of carbon in municipal solid waste, the flue gases released at the stack contain, on average, around 50% of biogenic CO₂. Thus, applying carbon capture technologies to EfW plants could allow negative CO₂ emissions [7,8], and CCS based on Calcium-Looping (CaL) is among the most promising solutions applicable to this sector [9]. This system has been studied in various industries, demonstrating high CO₂ removal efficiency with low energy and economic costs [9–14]. This technology is of particular interest for WtE plants due to the flexibility in fuel use and the possibility of using Municipal Solid Waste (MSW) and Refuse Derived Fuel (RDF) as the oxy-calcination heat source for the regeneration of the calcium-based sorbent used in the CO₂ capture process [15].

The core of both partial oxyfuel and CaL processes is oxy-calcination, which generates a stream with a CO₂ concentration of 70-90%_{vol,dry}. This stream needs further purification to reach the purity standards required for CO₂ transport and storage, which are project-specific and, in most cases, require a minimum CO₂ concentration of 95%_{vol,dry} [16,17]. The Compression and Purification Unit (CPU), which processes the CO₂-rich gas from the calciner, allows producing very high purity (>99.99%_{vol,dry}) liquid CO₂; by contrast, the CPU, after purification, still leaves a fraction of the captured CO₂ together with the non-condensables in the vent gas (due to its finite selectivity and recovery, especially when very high CO₂ purities are required). For example, the CPU vent gases from a 1 Mt_{clik}/y cement plant operating in partial oxyfuel configuration and a 500 kt/y WtE plant using CaL could still contain up to 50-100 ktCO₂/y, [18]. Therefore, optimizing the integration of the CPU with the whole capture process is essential to achieve significant emission reductions in both sectors utilizing oxyfuel-based CO₂ capture technologies.

The EU Horizon HERCCULES [19] project's primary goal is to accelerate the development of the entire CO₂ supply chain (capture, storage, and utilization) through demonstration plants integrated within real operating cement and EfW facilities. In this framework, two pilot plants will be built connected to a cement plant owned by TITAN (partial oxyfuel pilot plant) and an EfW owned by A2A (CaL pilot plant). Both pilot plants will consist of a configuration that

integrates the CO₂ capture process with the CPU, recovering its vent gases to demonstrate the maximum carbon footprint reduction of both technologies.

This work will present the technological details of the two pilot plants built as part of the HERCCULES project and present the plant's main energy KPIs for estimating the reduction of CO₂ emissions, energy consumption and the potential for the development of circular economies, such as the production of secondary cementitious materials.

Nomenclature

CaL	Calcium-Looping
CCA	Cost of CO ₂ Avoided
CCUS	Carbon Capture Utilization and Storage
CFD	Computational Fluid Dynamics
CPU	Compression and Purification Unit
EfW	Energy-from-Waste
ETS	European Trading Systems
FEED	Front End Engineering Design
IEA	International Energy Agency
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MSW	Municipal Solid Waste
PCC	Post-Combustion Capture
RDF	Refuse Derived Fuel
SCM	Supplementary Cementitious Material
SPECCA	Specific Primary Energy Consumption per CO ₂ Avoided
SRF	Solid Recovered Fuel
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
WP	Work Package

2. The HERCCULES project

The HERCCULES project is an innovation action in the framework of the Horizon Europe research programme, aimed at demonstrating, for the first time, the feasibility of the whole CCUS chain in southern Europe, with a particular focus on the decarbonization of two strategic clusters located in northern Italy and Greece and two hard to abate sectors such as cement and energy-from-waste, and a significant effort to reach the ambitious targets is dedicated to the demonstration activities of the pilot plants. The partnership comprises nine research organizations and fourteen industrial partners, including top European universities, research centers, critical players in the energy production, waste management and cement production sectors, and several technology providers. Fig. 1 (left) shows the various partners and the location within Europe.

Three CO₂ capture systems will be tested and are currently in the design phase; the partial-oxyfuel calciner and an amine-based solvent absorption system will be installed in a cement plant, and the CaL solution will be built in an EfW plant. Three CO₂ utilization pilots will assess the mineralization of part of the captured CO₂: (i) an autoclave to demonstrate the integration between the cement and EfW sectors using part of the purge from the CaL installed in the waste treatment plant to produce autoclaved hydraulic binders; (ii) a skid for the mineralization of fine demolished concrete to test the possibility of mineralize the CO₂ from the partial oxyfuel system used for the pre-calcination process of the cement plant; and (iii) a zeolite-based CO₂ mineralization plant to assess the possibility of generating CO₂-trapped natural and synthetic zeolite to be used as Supplementary Cementitious Materials (SCMs). Finally, the two most advanced CO₂ storage sites in southern Europe, Ravenna and Prinos, operated by ENI and Energean, respectively, will be used to test the storage feasibility. During the five years of the project, the test facilities will be

operated for more than 10'000 hours, capturing and storing more than 3'500 and 1'000 tonnes of CO₂, respectively, and producing more than 8'000 tonnes of low-carbon concrete.

Fig. 1 (right) shows the project's structure, highlighting the interaction between the various Work Packages (WPs). WP1 focuses on project management, and WP10 focuses on results communications and dissemination; due to the nature of the related activities, they are transversal to the rest of the WPs and span the entire project timeline. The other WPs are organized into three blocks: (i) on the demonstration of CCUS processes and technologies, in particular, CO₂ capture in cement (WP2) and EfW plants (WP3), CO₂ utilization and resource circularity (WP4), and CO₂ transportation and storage (WP5); (ii) on the technologies upscaling, with WP6 on the design and optimization of the CCUS chain integration and industrial clustering, and WP7 on the exploitation of the results by delivering pre-FEED studies of the tested technologies; and (iii) on socio-economic strategies, including WP8 on social and regulatory elements and WP9 on business and financial aspects of the CCUS chain. The overall project budget is around 40 M€, 30 of which corresponds to the EU contribution and will last five years.

We are currently in the first phase of the project, dedicated to modelling and designing the CO₂ capture plants, and we have also started procuring the test facilities both for cement and EfW plants. Furthermore, next year, we will start operating the new generation amine-based post-combustion capture system, which will be installed in the Vernasca cement plant operated by Buzzi Unicem. By the end of next year, we will start a crucial phase for the project, testing and demonstrating the hybrid capture technology, which will be installed in the Greek cement plant operated by Titan and the post-combustion calcium looping process at the EfW plant located in Milan and operated by A2A. We will demonstrate the technologies at TRL 7-8; thus, they are not full-scale applications but of significant size and in relevant environments, and all the results will be exploited for the design and optimization of the transportation networks in the northern Italy and Greece clusters.

In the second part of the project, we will demonstrate the CO₂ utilization processes, focusing on mineralization systems, and finally, we will also demonstrate the CO₂ transportation, injection and permanent storage in Ravenna and Prinos. At the end of the project, we will deliver exploitation material, business plans, and guidelines for all the technologies we are demonstrating, as well as a life cycle assessment and cost-benefit analysis of the whole CCUS chain for the selected case study. To reach the final goal of preparing the full-scale implementation of the CCUS network in the Italian and Greek clusters.

Fig. 1. Partner list and location (left) and work package structure (right) of the HERCCULES project.

3. Carbon capture demonstration plant in cement plant

Concerning the CO₂ capture technologies demonstrated in the cement plant, two stand-alone processes and their combination, the so-called hybrid configuration, will be tested. The experimental campaigns will be focused on establishing the technologies at TRL 7-8, while the scale-up studies will assess the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), such as the purity and capture rate of the CO₂, the Specific Primary Energy Consumption per CO₂ Avoided (SPECCA), the specific CO₂ emission, and the Cost of CO₂ Avoided (CCA). According to preliminary evaluations, the hybrid configuration achieves the best performance using Solid Recovered Fuels (SRFs) as the energy source in the calciner with a SPECCA less than 2.2 MJ_{LHV}/kg_{CO2} and a CCA lower than 50 €/t_{CO2} while allowing negative CO₂ emission of around 150 kg_{CO2}/t_{clinker}.

The first technology is the partial oxyfuel process that captures the CO₂ generated by the raw material calcination, which is the most considerable portion, and by the oxidation of the fuel fed to the calciner to provide the heat required by the endothermic reaction. Once dried, the flue gas generated by the oxy-combustion process is already rich in CO₂ and can be purified with a cryogenic unit to meet transportation specifications. In this case, achieving an overall reduction of 80% of the cement plant emission is possible even if the rotary kiln flue gas is not decarbonized. The second technology is a new-generation post-combustion amine-based capture system, which can be used to decarbonize the calciner and kiln flue gases and implemented using several configurations featuring a membrane contactor reactor and lean vapour recompressor. The hybrid configuration uses the oxyfuel technology for the calciner, and both the kiln flue gas and the calciner purification unit vent gas, which still contains a fraction of the CO₂ mixed with the incondensable gases, are treated by the post-combustion system. In this way, achieving both high CO₂ purity and a capture rate of up to 98% is possible. Fig. 2 (left) shows the hybrid configuration's simplified block flow diagram.

The demonstration of the oxyfuel and hybrid configurations will be carried out in the cement plant operated by Titan in Greece, while the stand-alone Post-Combustion Capture (PCC) system will be tested in the Vernasca cement plant operated by Buzzi Unicem in Italy.

The oxyfuel demonstration plant will feature a calciner with a thermal power input of 1.5 MW_{LHV}, able to use both alternative solid fuels and natural gas as heat source, a cryogenic CO₂ purification and liquefaction unit delivering between 4.5 and 5 tonnes per day of liquid CO₂ and a mineralization unit for the utilization of the CO₂ remaining in the CPU vent gas which will produce around 1'000 tonnes of SCMs at a nominal production rate of around 1.5 tonnes per hour. The expected CO₂ capture rate is around 80%.

Fig. 2 (right) shows a simplified block diagram of the oxyfuel demonstration plant. A cyclone at the exit of the calciner separates the calcinated material and sends it to the cement plant kiln, while the raw meal is injected in the remaining CO₂-rich gas to be preheated, then a second cyclone separates the gas from the raw meal to feed the oxy-calciner. Finally, part of the cooled gas stream is mixed with oxygen and recycled to the combustor to moderate the flame temperature. The calciner has been designed to operate with petcoke and natural gas as fuels and with a minimum gas velocity at the reactor exit of 17 m/s. The oxygen will be regulated to achieve an oxygen concentration in the outlet stream of 3.5%_{vol,dry}, while the oxygen concentration in the oxidant stream at the burner inlet will be tuned by controlling the recycled CO₂-rich gas and will be between 21% and 50%. Finally, the raw meal flow rate will regulate the reactor outlet temperature at around 920°C. The design aims to retrofit the current infrastructure to support the demonstration plant, minimizing the modification requirement at the existing plant.

The process simulations indicate a preliminary reactor height of around 30 meters to achieve the target calcination degree of 90%. Furthermore, the various models developed, with multiple degrees of complexity, from 0D to 3D, produce similar results, indicating a calcination degree between 89% and 92% and an outlet temperature between 900°C and 920°C. The accordance between the models suggests that they are suitable for further investigation of the process, and thus, they will be used as the design of the system is refined from the preliminary configuration to the proposed version for the construction. In particular, LUT has developed, using an in-house code, detailed 1D and 3D models of the reactor to provide necessary reactor height and details on the distribution and hydrodynamics, and a CFD model of the bottom part, using Ansys Fluent, to investigate temperature and particle distribution, and in particular mixing of fuel and raw meal, in the reactor splash box.

Fig. 2. Hybrid configuration's simplified block flow diagram (left), and simplified block diagram of the oxyfuel demonstration plant (right).

4. Carbon capture demonstration plant in EfW plant

The calcium looping system for CO₂ capture in EfW plants will be demonstrated at TRL 7-8 at the A2A site in Italy using the configuration depicted in Fig. 3 (left), coupling the capture process with the purification unit. Furthermore, preliminary lab experiments will characterize the Ca-based sorbent exposed to EfW flue gases.

The plant's flue gas is sent to the carbonator reactor with the calcium oxide sorbent, which, reacting with the CO₂, captures it, producing calcium carbonate sent to the calcinator for regeneration. The fuel for the endothermic calcination reaction is SRF, and the released CO₂, both from the sorbent's regeneration and the fuel's oxidation, is sent to a cryogenic purification unit, with the target objective of 95% capture rate and high CO₂ purity above 99.9%_{vol,dry}. The scale-up and techno-economic analysis will focus on achieving negative CO₂ emissions, around 400 kgCO₂/t_{waste}, and improving the net electric efficiency of the plant by 3 percentage points compared to the benchmark MEA-based capture system.

The calcium looping pilot plant will focus its analysis on the influence of key operating parameters on the overall performance, focusing on the integration between the capture system and the purification unit, which will be studied by recycling the CPU vent gas at the carbonator inlet. Finally, the pilot plant will allow quantifying the negative effects of air infiltration and higher CPU temperature on the system performance.

The expected results, derived from preliminary simulations, show that recycling the CPU vent increases the capture efficiency from 75% to 95% while decreasing the amount of flue gas that can be treated by the demo plant and increasing the produced CO₂ due to the higher CO₂ concentration in the CPU vent compared to the plant flue gas.

The model validation of the calcium looping system has been carried out by Sumitomo SHI-FW considering a design carbonator and calciner temperatures of 650°C and 900°C, a sorbent makeup and circulating flow rate of 0.2 and 12 compared to the CO₂ flow rate in the flue gas, and a thermal duty of 1 MW_{th}. On the other hand, the model validation of the CPU has been carried out by TPI considering a stripper temperature of 20 bar, corresponding to a reboiler temperature of around -18°C and a condenser temperature of -37°C. Liquid CO₂ will have less than 10 ppm_{vol} of oxygen to meet transportation specifics, and part of it will be used to cool down the condenser top gas to -46°C and maximize the capture efficiency.

The preliminary simulations carried out by LEAP and Politecnico di Milano have considered, in addition to the design case, four additional off-design scenarios: (i) increasing the air leakage in the calcium looping system from 3%

to 7%; (ii) increasing the CPU minimum temperature from -46°C to -40°C ; (iii) increasing the oxygen content in the calcinatory oxidant stream from 40%_{vol} to 60%_{vol}; and (iv) decreasing the sorbent makeup and circulating flow rate from 0.2/12 to 0.1/8 (as molar ratio with the CO_2 flow rate in the gas stream at the carbonator inlet). As stated before, the pilot plant aims at assessing the influence of the operating parameters on the overall performance, and, in addition to the CPU vent recycle, the test will show the impact of the fuel composition, the reactors' temperatures, the oxygen concentration, and the solid mass flow rates, while meeting CO_2 characteristic for transportation.

Sumitomo SHI-FW is currently carrying out basic engineering and detailed design of the calcium looping system and its relative auxiliaries. Fig. 3 (right) shows a preliminary 3D layout view of the circulating fluidized bed carbonator and calciner. Similarly, TPI is developing the engineering of the cryogenic purification unit, which will also include several pretreatment systems, such as an ejector for humidity and dust removal, an acid scrubber, a heavy metal filter, in addition to the core components, a stripper column, condenser and vent condenser. The stripper condenser will be cooled by a dedicated CO_2 cycle, while the vent condenser will use part of the produced CO_2 .

Fig. 3. Configuration of the CaL demonstration capture system at the EfW plant (left), and preliminary 3D layout view of the circulating fluidized bed carbonator and calciner (right).

5. Conclusions and next steps

The Horizon Europe HERCCULES project is an innovation action aimed at assessing the whole CCUS chain in southern Europe, focusing on the cement and EfW sectors. A significant effort to achieve this ambitious goal is dedicated to demonstrating CO_2 capture and utilization technologies.

Three capture technologies will be tested in the cement industry. An amine-based solvent absorption system will be first installed at the cement plant operated by Buzzi Unicem in Vernasca, Italy, to assess the performance of a new generation solvent using several configurations and including innovative components, such as a membrane contactor absorber and a lean vapour recompressor to reduce the specific energy consumption. On the other hand, an oxyfuel calciner coupled with a CPU will be installed at the plant operated by Titan in Thessaloniki, Greece, to evaluate the possibility of achieving a capture rate of around 80% by capturing the CO_2 released in the calcination process from the decomposition of the raw material ($\text{CaCO}_3 \rightarrow \text{CaO} + \text{CO}_2$) and the oxidation of the fuel without modifying the key steps of the clinker production process in the rotary kiln and in clinker cooler. Finally, the PPC system will be transported to the Thessaloniki plant, and the hybrid configuration will be tested using the ammine-based plant to capture the CO_2 in the rotary kiln flue gas and CPU vent gas, aiming to achieve an overall capture rate of 98%.

In the EfW plant of A2A in Milan, Italy, a CaL system coupled with a cryogenic CPU will be installed to assess the decarbonization performance of this system compared to a benchmark ammine-based post-combustion solution. This system requires a continuous makeup and purge of sorbent from the reactors to maintain high reactivity. The extracted material can be used to produce autoclaved hydraulic binders, demonstrating the integration between the cement and EfW sectors. Furthermore, two other CO₂ utilization technologies will be tested in addition to the autoclave system: a skid for the mineralization of fine demolished concrete using the CO₂ from the partial oxyfuel system and a zeolite-based mineralization plant to produce CO₂-trapped natural and synthetic zeolite to be used as SCMs.

Currently, all the capture and utilization technologies are in the design and procurement stage, and next year, starting with the new generation PCC system, the experimental campaign will begin. TPI designed the ammine-based system and the cryogenic CPU for the CaL system, Sumitomo SHI-FW is carrying out the basic engineering and detailed design of the calcium looping demonstrator for the EfW plant, and Titan, through a subcontractor, is developing the oxyfuel calciner. Finally, regarding the utilization technologies, the industrial partners will provide the autoclave system for the CO₂ mineralization with the CaL purge, Buzzi Unicem will realize the zeolite-based mineralization plant, and LEAP, through a subcontractor, will rent the mineralization skid for fine demolished concrete with the CO₂ from the oxyfuel calciner.

In the final phase of the project, also CO₂ storage will be assessed using part of the captured CO₂ from the demonstration plant and exploiting the two most advanced geological storage sites in southern Europe, Ravenna and Prinos, respectively, in Italy and Greece and operate by ENI and Energean. Furthermore, the development of the whole CCUS chain will be optimized for the northern Italy and Greece clusters.

Exploitation material, business plans, and guidelines for all the technologies demonstrated, as well as a life cycle assessment and cost-benefit analysis of the whole CCUS, will be delivered at the end of the project.

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References

- [1] International Energy Agency (IEA). World Energy outlook 2024. Paris: 2024.
- [2] International Energy Agency (IEA). Net Zero Roadmap: A Global Pathway to Keep the 1.5 °C Goal in Reach. Paris: 2023.
- [3] De Lena E, Cremona R, Spinelli M, Gatti M, Romano MC, Lindemann Lino M. Final performance of the optimized CaL processes in full scale cement plants using validated reactor models. 2022.
- [4] Gimenez M, Paxton C, Wassard H, Mogensen O, Paubel X, Leclerc M, et al. The oxycombustion option. *International Cement Review* 2014;37–43.
- [5] Hoening V, Hoppe H, Koring K, Lemke J. ECRA CCS Project – Report on Phase III. Duesseldorf: 2012.
- [6] Barker D, Holmes D, Hunt J, Napier-Moore P, Turner S, Clark M. CO₂ Capture in the Cement Industry. Cheltenham: 2008.
- [7] Creutzig F, Ravindranath NH, Berdes G, Bolwig S, Bright R, Cherubini F, et al. Bioenergy and climate change mitigation: an assessment. *GCB Bioenergy* 2015;7:916–44. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcbb.12205>.
- [8] Gough C, Thornley P, Mander S, Vaughan N, Falano T, editors. Biomass Energy with Carbon Capture and Storage (BECCS): Unlocking Negative Emissions. Chichester, UK: John Wiley & Sons, Ltd; 2018. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781119237716>.
- [9] Haaf M, Anantharaman R, Roussanaly S, Ströhle J, Epple B. CO₂ capture from waste-to-energy plants: Techno-economic assessment of novel integration concepts of calcium looping technology. *Resour Conserv Recycl* 2020;162:104973. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2020.104973>.
- [10] Astolfi M, De Lena E, Casella F, Romano MC. Calcium looping for power generation with CO₂ capture: The potential of sorbent storage for improved economic performance and flexibility. *Appl Therm Eng* 2021;194:117048. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.applthermaleng.2021.117048>.
- [11] Atsonios K, Grammelis P, Antiohos SK, Nikolopoulos N, Kakaras Em. Integration of calcium looping technology in existing cement plant for CO₂ capture: Process modeling and technical considerations. *Fuel* 2015;153:210–23. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fuel.2015.02.084>.
- [12] De Lena E, Arias B, Romano MC, Abanades JC. Integrated Calcium Looping System with Circulating Fluidized Bed Reactors for Low CO₂

- Emission Cement Plants. *International Journal of Greenhouse Gas Control* 2022;114:103555. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijggc.2021.103555>.
- [13] Lena E De, Spinelli M, Gatti M, Scaccabarozzi R, Campanari S, Consonni S, et al. Techno-economic analysis of calcium looping processes for low CO₂ emission cement plants. *International Journal of Greenhouse Gas Control* 2019;82:244–60. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijggc.2019.01.005>.
- [14] Ozcan DC, Ahn H, Brandani S. Process integration of a Ca-looping carbon capture process in a cement plant. *International Journal of Greenhouse Gas Control* 2013;19:530–40. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijggc.2013.10.009>.
- [15] Haaf M, Hilz J, Peters J, Unger A, Ströhle J, Epple B. Operation of a 1 MWth calcium looping pilot plant firing waste-derived fuels in the calciner. *Powder Technol* 2020;372:267–74. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.powtec.2020.05.074>.
- [16] International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 27913:2016 - Carbon dioxide capture, transportation and geological storage - Pipeline transportation systems. 2016.
- [17] Equinor. Northern Lights Project Concept report - RE-PM673-00001. 2019.
- [18] Magli F, Spinelli M, Fantini M, Romano MC, Gatti M. Techno-economic optimization and off-design analysis of CO₂ purification units for cement plants with oxyfuel-based CO₂ capture. *International Journal of Greenhouse Gas Control* 2022;115:103591. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijggc.2022.103591>.
- [19] Laboratorio Energia Ambiente Piacenza (LEAP). HERCCULES website 2024. <https://www.herccules.eu/> (accessed December 4, 2024).